

Growth performance of maize (*Zea mays L*) cultivated in soils treated with varying physical forms of swine waste at Umuagwo

Amanze C. T^{1*}, Ukabiala M. E¹, Nwawuike N², Amulu L. U³, Nwosu O. U².

¹Department of Soil Science, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo.

²Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo.

³Department of Crop Science, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo.

*Corresponding author: chikamneleamanze@gmail.com

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Abstract: Plant growth could be influenced by soil condition, and used to predict soil fertility. A field trial in RCBD was carried-out to assess growth performance of local maize cultivated on soils treated with different physical forms of swine waste (decomposed, fresh, crushed dry swine waste, and fresh swine waste dispersed in water) replicated thrice. Treatments (10 tons / ha each) were randomly applied on plots (2 m X 1 m each) arranged in three blocks. Maize seeds were planted after treatments application at spacing of 75 cm x 25 cm. Plant parameters (stem diameter, plant height, and leaf area) were measured at 4 and 6 weeks after germination (WAG). Data obtained were subjected to ANOVA, T – test, and correlation analysis using SPSS version 23. Results showed that treatments were not significantly different ($P \leq 5\%$) in influencing maize plant growth at 4 WAG and 6 WAG; however, at 4 WAG, swine waste dispersed in water had the highest values of 1.50 cm, 29.00 cm, and 203.50 cm² for stem diameter, plant height and leaf area, respectively, while fresh swine waste had the lowest values of 1.08 cm, 19.71 cm, and 75.39 cm², respectively. At 6 WAG, fresh swine waste had highest stem diameter (2.07 cm), while decomposed swine waste had lowest value for stem diameter (1.72 cm) and leaf area (233.00 cm²). Application of fresh swine waste dispersed in water promotes growth of maize plant, and it is therefore recommended, while decomposed swine waste should be avoided.

Keywords: stem diameter, plant height, leaf area, swine waste, maize plant.

Introduction

Soil fertility status is a relevant factor in determining the performance of crops, including their growth conditions (Liu, 2024). The growth condition of crop on a given soil can serve as an indicator the fertility level of the soil, provided that other external and internal growth factors are kept constant (Liu, 2024). Generally, soil as a medium of plant growth serves to provide crops with nutrients (N, P, K, etc), water, air, and anchor as may be conditioned by its chemical compositions (pH, essential nutrient element composition, etc.), structural architecture as influenced by soil texture and organic matter content, which in turn influence bulk density, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, permeability, and water retention characteristics (Infan et., 2023).

Maize plant is very sensitive to soil infertility and could easily manifest the deficiency symptoms including those associated with growth such as such as; stunted growth, reduced leaf area, slenderness or thin and weak stem, etc; these symptoms have often ended in poor maize performance, loss of yield, maize crop failure, economic waste, and declined food production (Mohammad et al, 2023). It is on record that maize plant serves as a source of staple food for most

countries of the world including Nigeria; it also serves as a source of feed for livestock (Monday, 2018); therefore, any factor (including soil fertility) that hampers the optimum to maximum performance of maize plant poses a hunger threat to the teeming population of the world (Monday, 2018).

The recognition of soil infertility as one of the major limitations of maize production, most farmers across the world including farmers in southeast Nigeria have over the years resolved to use mineral fertilizers (NPK formulations) to optimize the growing of maize, and this is because of the ability of mineral fertilizers to avail crops with the needed nutrients with ease (Oluyede, 2007). However, the current high cost of mineral fertilizers, the environmental hazards associated with the application of mineral fertilizers, and the rising need for organic farming have reawakened farmers consciousness to the use of organic manure such as swine waste, poultry droppings, traditional liming materials, biochar, etc., with the aim of improving soil fertility for optimum maize performance (Daily Trust, 2022). Most organic materials including pig waste have proven to possess good fertilizer property by their possession of mineralizable nutrient elements and ability to improve soil reaction which enhances nutrients release and availability (Gerrard and

Amy, 2020). Notwithstanding, the challenge in the use of organic manure is slow release of nutrients, and this causes the needed nutrients to remain below their critical levels making it difficult for the plant to receive minimum nutrition; consequently, the crop suffers hidden hunger with associated loss of yield in the end, or immediately manifests deficiency symptoms (Gerald and Army, 2020).

There is the speculation every organic manure type has a particular physical form of it which can enhance soil fertility and provide crops with nutrients within the shortest possible time; hence, enhance the growth and productivity of the crop such as maize plant (Kelvin and Tom, 2022). This study therefore aims at assessing the growth performance of maize plant cultivated on soils amended with varying physical forms of swine waste.

Materials and Method

Description of study area

The study was carried out at the demonstration farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo (UAES) in Imo State, Nigeria. The area lies within the geographical coordinates of 5°15' N to 5°33' N of latitude and 6°31' E of longitude. The climate is characterized with the wet and dry seasons which features from March to

October, and November to February, respectively. However, the wet season has a bimodal rainfall pattern with a short period of decline in rainfall intensity which occurs in August (August break). The mean annual rainfall is 2200 mm and mean annual temperature of 28°C (Nwawuiké et al., 2023). The soil is formed on the Coastal Plain Sands and belongs to the Order “Ultisols” according to the United State Department of Agriculture (USDA) soil taxonomical classification (Amanze et al., 2016).

Site characterization

The land was under 2 – year fallow, characterized with the presence of plant species common to a secondary vegetation in a tropical rainforest vegetation zone. The soil texture ranges from loamy sand to sand, it is slightly to moderately acidic, low to moderate in basic cations and cation exchange capacity, low to moderate in available phosphorus, moderate to high in organic carbon, and low to moderate in total nitrogen (Nwawuiké et al., 2023). The soil was dry at the first few weeks of the experiment as conditioned by the weather of the dry season (February to early March).

Treatments and treatments preparation

Four (4) treatments were used for this research, and they were; fresh swine waste

(FSW), fresh swine waste dispersed in water (WDS), decomposed swine waste (DEC), and crushed dry swine waste (DCS). The swine waste was sourced from a pig farm in the UAES as fresh swine waste. Some portions for DEC were poured inside a pit and covered with plant materials, then let for about two weeks, but periodically turned to facilitate its decomposition. Some portions for DSC were air-dried and crushed. Meanwhile, on the day of treatments application, another set of fresh swine waste were obtained from the same source; 10 tons / ha equivalent (2 kg) was measured and dispersed in water ready for application, while the remaining portion served for the fresh swine waste.

Source of planting material

The planting material was local yellow maize variety sourced from a local market at Umuagwo Ohaji Egbema Owerri, Imo State.

Field work

Land preparation, plot allocation and seedbed preparation.

The land was cleared of the existing vegetation and the area marked out. The area was partitioned into three (3) blocks separated by space of 1 m apart. Four plots (seedbeds) of 2m X 1m were marked out in each block, and the plots were separated by distance of 50

cm apart. Low lying seedbeds were prepared manually while maintaining the plot dimensions.

Treatments application and planting of test crop

The four treatments were randomly assigned to each plot in each block, then incorporated in to the soil. On the same day, the maize seeds were planted in a spacing of 75 cm X 25 cm while giving space allowance of 25 cm from the edges of the beds. The seeds were sown to 2 seeds per hole.

Cultural practices

After seed germination, the seedlings were thinned to one plant per stand to give total of nine (9) plants per plot, 36 plants per block, and total population 108 plants. Weeds were periodically removed manually, and irrigation water was periodically applied at the peak of the dry season until the rain established.

Plant Sampling

Four (4) plants were randomly selected in each plot and marked for sampling. The plants were samples at two sampling periods namely; 4 weeks and 6 weeks after seed germination. The plants were sampled for plant height, leaf area and stem diameter. Plant height was

measured using a measuring tape and the height was taken from the base of the plant to the point where the last leaf emanated from the stem. Stem girth was measured using an improvised caliper, while the leaf area was measured using meter rule by measuring the length, and widths of the leaf from the base of the leaf, middle point and close to its tip, then average width of the leaf was obtained by calculation. The leaf area was then estimated as the product of the length and average width of the leaf.

Experimental design and Data analyses

The experiment was laid-out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) involving four (4) treatments and replicated three (3) times to give a total of twelve (12) treatments plots. Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), T – test, and

correlation analysis using SPSS analytical software version 23.

Results and discussions

Variation of leaf area of maize plants among the treatments

Figure 1 shows the mean values of maize plants leaf area at the various treated soils at two different sampling period. The results revealed that there is no significant ($P \leq 5\%$) variation in the leaf area of the maize plants at the various treated soils in the two sampling periods. Notwithstanding, at the first sampling period, WDS had the highest mean value (203.50 cm²) for leaf area while FSW had the lowest (75.39 cm²); but in the second sampling period, DCS gave the highest mean leaf area (330.00 cm²) followed by WDS (320.00 cm²), while DEC produced maize plants with the lowest mean leaf area of 233.00 cm².

LSD_(0.05) for T1 = 35.01006 ; LSD_(0.05) for T2 = 56.63847

WDS is fresh swine waste dispersed in water, FSW is fresh swine waste, DEC is decomposed swine waste, DCS is dried and crushed sw

Figure 1 Variation of leaf area (cm²) among treatments over time

Variation of maize plants stem diameter and height among the treatments

Variation in stem diameter of the maize plants at the various treated soils at different sampling periods are shown in Figure 2. The values indicate that there was no significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) in stem diameter of the plants at the various treated soils in the two sampling periods. However, at the first sampling period (4 WAG), WDS had the highest stem diameter (1.50 cm) while FSW had the lowest (1.08 cm), but in the second sampling period (6 WAG), FSW had the highest stem diameter (2.07 cm) followed by

WDS (1.99 cm), while DEC had the lowest (1.72 cm).

Figure 3. Shows the mean values of maize plant height at the various treated soils at the two sampling periods. From the Figure, there was no significant difference in maize plant height at the various treated soils in the sampling periods. Meanwhile, the highest (29.00 cm) and lowest (19.71 cm) mean plant heights were observed at the WDS and FSW, respectively; but at the second sampling period, WDS had the highest mean value (67.67 cm) followed by FSW (61.33 cm), while DCS had the lowest mean plant height (49.67 cm).

LSD_(0.05) for T1 = 0.16437; LSD_(0.05) for T2 = 0.24112

WDS is fresh swine waste dispersed in water, FSW is fresh swine waste, DEC is decomposed swine waste, DCS is dried and crushed

Figure 2 Mean stem diameter (cm) of maize plants among the treatments

LSD_(0.05) for T1 = 3.85187; LSD_(0.05) for T2 = 9.94569

WDS is fresh swine waste dispersed in water, FSW is fresh swine waste, DEC is decomposed swine waste, DCS is dried and crushed swine was

Figure 3 Mean maize plants height (cm) among the treatments

The reason for the greatest performance of the growth parameters observed on maize plants grown on soil treated with fresh swine waste dispersed in water (WDS) at the first sampling period could be a result of the availability of soluble essential nutrient elements extracted from the manure by water, such as nitrogen, which served to boost the growth of the plant upon uptake before further mineralization overtime. Nitrogen is a very mobile element and shows high solubility in water in the form of nitrate ion which makes it readily available in soil solution (Infan *et al.*, 2023). Also, the large surface area of the manure facilitated by its dispersion in water may have largely exposed the particles of the manure and enhanced its decomposition by aiding the activities of decomposers in the soil; in addition, water may have improved the

moisture content of the dry soil to the level that activated microbial activities leading to increased decomposition and mineralization of organic compounds in the manure at that early stage (Kelvin & Tom, 2022). Conversely, the least growth performance observed on the maize plants grown on soil treated with fresh swine waste (FSW) was possibly a result of the reduced surface area of the manure, because it was in lumps, and the dryness of the soil which limited the area exposed for microbial decomposition and hampered activities of decomposers, accordingly. Soil moisture is a relevant factor in the overall assessment of soil fertility because plant nutrition is basically by water, and water helps to activated microbial activities and processes in the soil including

organic matter decomposition (Mohammad et al., 2023).

In the second sampling period, the highest stem diameter of maize plants at the soil treated with fresh swine waste (FSW) could be attributed to its disintegration by the first rain which possibly dissolved and caused the release of soluble nutrients such as nitrogen for plant uptake, however, the values of stem diameter, plant height and leaf area of maize plants at soil treated with fresh swine waste dispersed in water (WDS) implies that the WDS promoted the availability of nutrients to sustain significant growth of the maize plants. This may have been made possible by the increased decomposition and mineralization of the organic manure aided by its large surface area, rich nutrient composition due to its freshness, and availability of water to facilitate microbial breakdown, nutrient transformation, and availability for plant uptake (Kelvin and Tom, 2022; Amanze et al., 2024). Conversely, the least values of growth parameters observed at maize plants grown on soil treated with decomposed swine waste (DEC) could be predicted on the possible loss of nutrients such as nitrogen from the decomposed manure. Decomposition of organic materials release nitrogen in the form of ammonium and nitrates which are easily lost by volatilization, consumption by

decomposers, and leaching; hence, decomposed organic manure are deficient in some essential nutrient elements compared to their fresh counterpart. The implication is that the decomposed swine waste could not sustain the fertility of the soil overtime to promote significant growth of the maize plants.

Variation of the maize growth parameter with time

Table 1 presents the differences in the mean values of the maize plant growth parameters at the two sampling periods for the various treated soils. It shows that there was significant ($P \leq 5\%$) increase in the growth parameters of maize plant over the times at the various treated soils. The significant variation of each of the growth parameters in the two sampling periods at the respective treated soils is an indication that there is progressive release of nutrients from the manures into the soils to sustain notable progress in the growth of maize plants. This corroborates the report of Liu (2024) that progressive plant growth over time was sustained by the availability of essential nutrients such as nitrogen in the soil. Furthermore, organic manures are slow in nutrient release, and therefore serves to ensure the availability of nutrients in the soil over

expanded period of time for plant uptake resulting in sustained growth and development (Infan *et al.*, 2023).

Table 1 T – test comparison of the plant growth parameters for the two sampling periods at each treatment

Treatments	Growth parameters	Means of Sampling periods		Overall Mean	Std. Error Mean	Level of significance
		4WAP	6WAP			
WDS	Stem diameter (cm)	1.5033	1.9900	1.747	0.1119722	≤ 0.01
	Plant height (cm)	28.9967	67.6667	48.331	8.7566864	0.030
	Leaf area (cm ²)	203.5000	320.8333	262.167	31.7775293	≤ 0.01
DEC	Stem diameter (cm)	1.1300	1.7233	1.427	0.2100265	0.001
	Plant height (cm)	28.9967	56.0000	38.333	9.5277373	0.010
	Leaf area (cm ²)	203.5000	233.0000	160.221	43.6920832	0.014
FSW	Stem diameter (cm)	1.0767	2.0700	1.573	0.2276938	0.001
	Plant height (cm)	19.7100	61.3333	40.522	9.5118454	0.008
	Leaf area (cm ²)	75.3867	266.6667	171.027	44.6340205	0.012
DCS	Stem diameter (cm)	1.4967	1.9200	1.708	0.1153666	0.000
	Plant height (cm)	27.8900	49.6667	38.778	5.9241711	0.001
DCS	Leaf area (cm ²)	168.9433	330.1667	249.556	41.7035493	0.002

WDS is fresh swine waste dispersed in water, FSW is fresh swine waste, DEC is decomposed swine waste, DCS is dried and crushed swine waste

Relationships among the maize plant growth parameters

Table 2 shows the correlation matrix of the parameters. There is significant ($P \leq 0.01$) positive relationship between plant height and stem diameter at WDS (0.958**), FSW (0.990**), and DEC (0.924**), except at DCS (0.670) where the relationship was positive but not significant ($P \leq 0.05$). Plant height and leaf area have significant positive relationship at

the various treated soils except at DCS (0.543). However, the level of significance at the other treated soils varied such that at WDS (0.865*), the significance is at $P \leq 0.05$, while at FSW (0.956**) and DEC (0.969**), the significant level is $P \leq 0.01$. Also, there is positive significant ($P \leq 0.05$) relationship between stem diameter and leaf area of the maize plants at WSD (0.888*), DEC (0.895*), DCS (0.862*), but highly significant positive relationship at FSW (0.978**).

Table 2 Correlation matrix of the maize growth parameters under the various treatments

	WDS			FSW			DEC			DCS		
	SD	PH	LA	SD	PH	LA	SD	PH	LA	SD	PH	LA
SD	1			1			1			1		
PH	0.958**	1		0.990**	1		0.924**	1		0.670	1	
LA	0.888*	0.865*	1	0.978**	0.956**	1	0.895*	0.969**	1	0.862*	0.543	1

WDS is fresh swine waste dispersed in water, FSW is fresh swine waste, DEC is decomposed swine waste, DCS is dried and crushed swine waste, LA is leaf area, SD is stem diameter, PH is plant height, * is significant at $P \leq 0.05$, ** is significant at $P \leq 0.01$

The possible reason for the significant positive relationship among the growth parameters could be explained on the understanding that growth is a function of cell enlargement, division and differentiation. So, cells of the different parts of the plants (shoot, stem, Leaves, etc) upon uptake of nutrients undergo the processes of enlargement, division, and differentiation leading to irreversible increase in size and complexities of this various parts of the plant; hence, as the leaf is growing, same are the stem and shoot. However, the non-significant positive relationships between stem diameter and plant height; leaf area and plant height of plants at the soil treated with DEC could be a result of the possible disproportionate distribution of nutrients across the various parts of the plant such that parts of the plant that received greater amount of the nutrients grows at a faster rate independent of the other parts that received lesser amount. This may have happened at the soil treated with DEC

because of its possible lesser nutrient content to adequately supply the nutrient needs of the plants; hence, the minimal available nutrients may have been used up by the parts of the plant with higher demand for the nutrients than the others (Mohammad et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The various physical forms of swine waste are not significantly different in influencing the growth parameter of local maize plant. However, the fresh swine waste dispersed in water had the greatest level of positive influence on the maize growth parameters compared to the other physical forms of swine waste, while decomposed swine waste had the least positive influence on the growth parameters. Therefore, the best approach to the application of swine waste to improve growth parameters in maize plant is to disperse and apply it via irrigation water during dry season, or apply the fresh swine waste in crushed or dispersed form during the rainy season in hope of the rainwater. Efforts

should be made to avoid keeping swine waste to decompose before application.

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